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Toward the Sustainable Development of Machine Learning Applications in Industry 4.0

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TOWARD THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF MACHINE LEARNING APPLICATIONS IN INDUSTRY 4.0

Research Paper

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Abstract

As the level of digitization in industrial environments increases, companies are striving to improve efficiency and resilience to unplanned disruptions through the development of Machine Learning (ML)-based applications. Still, sustainable deployment and operation beyond proofs-of-concept is a challenging and resource-intensive task in dynamic environments such as industry 4.0, often impeding practical adoption in the long-term and thus sustainable ML product development. In this work, we systematically identify these challenges based on the CRISP-ML process model phases by applying a design science research approach. To this end, we conducted 15 interviews with data science practitioners in industry 4.0. Following a qualitative content analysis, design requirements and design principles for the development and sustainable long-term deployment of ML systems are derived to address identified challenges such as robustness to, and management of data drift caused by time-dependencies and machine/product differences, missing metadata, interfaces to other IT systems, expectation management, and MLOps guidelines.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Industry 4.0, Long-term Deployment, Design Science Research

1 Introduction

Machine Learning (ML)-based applications increasingly transcend from academia to operationally used applications in a multitude of industry sectors. Nevertheless, sustainable deployment and operation of ML-based applications beyond proofs-of-concept and prototypes is a challenging and resource-intensive task with various possibilities of project failure. Especially the long-term operation of ML applications poses several difficulties that are often not considered in academic research such as decaying accuracy due to the dynamic nature of the environment and the usage by non-experts. (Rudin and Wagstaff, 2014; Jourdan et al., 2021; Salama, Kazmierczak and Schut, 2021) Still, long-term operation is paramount to justify investments in the development of ML applications and to maximize the benefits that ML offers (McKinsey Global Institute, 2021; Vela et al., 2022). In addition to economic reasons, sustainable product development also requires that the value of a product, such as an ML application, which has consumed large amounts of resources during its development, be maintained over time (Klöpffer, 2003; van Wynsberghe, 2021).

Due to the rising levels of digitization in today's factories, industry 4.0 related applications have received significant attention in this context (Wuest et al., 2016; Fahle, Prinz and Kuhlentötter, 2020). Information technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT) and the interconnectivity of industry 4.0

transform manufacturing lines into Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS), which yield large amounts of data (Cassoli et al., 2022). Moreover, industry 4.0 related processes such as manufacturing operations are vital parts of their respective companies' value streams and naturally consume large amounts of resources, yielding high optimization potential (Wuest et al., 2016). Thus, companies in industry 4.0 strive to use the available data to improve effectiveness, efficiency and the resilience of their operations against unplanned disturbances to gain competitive advantages. However, in 2021, a study focusing on the manufacturing industry in Germany showed that two-thirds of ML applications developed in the participating companies did not surpass the concept development and prototyping stage, which hints at a significant untapped potential in the industry (Metternich et al., 2021). Overall, ML applications in the scope of industry 4.0 provide a particularly interesting context for our study because, first, ML applications offer high potential in this sector and ongoing investments already call for long-term operation (McKinsey Global Institute, 2021), second, frequent changes occur especially in manufacturing processes (Jourdan et al., 2021) and third, operators that use ML applications in this context usually do not have ML knowledge (Wuest et al., 2016), thus posing special challenges for long-term deployment. In this study, we refer to the specific context of industry 4.0 and can thus investigate how ML applications should be designed to enable long-term deployment in dynamic environments, which in turn has applications in different industries.

Information Systems (IS) research on ML applications in organizations also shifted focus to long-term deployment of ML applications and calls for continuous auditing and altering activities for adapting ML models to dynamic changes in problem perception. While several studies highlight the need for continuous maintenance of ML applications after they have been deployed, the integration of human feedback as a solution for model adaptation continues to be a focus of attention (e.g., Grønsund and Aanestad, 2020; Asatiani et al., 2021; Sturm et al., 2021). However, previous research still thinks too short and intervenes only during the deployment phase of ML, which in practice is often too late to smoothly adapt ML applications to dynamic changes. Many system properties, which are of central importance for the later adaptation of the models, are already determined and implemented in early project phases of ML application development. Thus, we see the need for a holistic approach that takes all phases of ML development and deployment into account and provides clear guidance on how to design ML applications that support the goal of long-term deployment in any ML project, especially in industry 4.0. If ML applications continue to be designed in a way that makes future adaptation difficult, there is a risk that large investments in this area will continue to be associated with little long-term impact. We aim to provide guidance in how to develop ML applications that provide the flexibility and adaptability required for long-term use in dynamic environments. Therefore, we are interested in the predominant technical and organizational challenges of sustainable ML implementation and use the context of industry 4.0 to ask how future research as well as practitioners that aim at designing, developing and deploying ML applications can address these challenges, leading to the following research questions (RQs):

In the context of industry 4.0, (RQ1) which challenges impede the sustainable development and deployment of ML systems, and (RQ2) how should ML systems be designed to overcome those challenges in order to ensure sustainable long-term deployment?

To address our two research questions, we apply a Design Science Research (DSR) approach that allows us to structure the given problem and derive design requirements and principles in order to conceptualize suggested solutions (Kuechler and Vaishnavi, 2008). We start with reviewing the popular Cross Industry Standard Process for Data Mining (CRISP-DM) (Wirth and Hipp, 2000) and the more recent CRISP-ML (Studer et al., 2021) for project management of ML applications in industrial settings, focusing on sustainability and long-term operation support to derive a structure for further analysis. As the main contribution of this study, semi-structured interviews are conducted with 15 data science and machine learning practitioners in the industry 4.0 sector. Challenges identified in these interviews are structured according to the CRISP-ML model and respective solution approaches to avoid these pitfalls and ensure for sustainability of ML applications are derived as design requirements and design principles to ensure ML applications have a long-term impact on industry and society. While many ML projects use the DSR approach, in the future we would like to enable these projects to incorporate sustainability considerations

and maintain the long-term value of their ML application, into which large amounts of resources have been poured during development.

2 Related Work

The following section provides an overview of the characteristics of ML and the corresponding process models that structure ML development projects. In addition, related studies that explore the need for continuous adaptation of ML applications in dynamic environments are presented.

2.1 Definition of ML and process models for structuring ML projects

Today, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and especially ML as a subfield of AI is deployed in various industries. In general, ML is defined as an approach that uses learning algorithms to derive patterns from data in order to build models that can solve real-world problems (Mitchell, 1997; Russell and Norvig, 2016; Brynjolfsson and Mitchell, 2017). In addition, different forms of ML have emerged of which supervised, unsupervised and reinforcement learning are the most common ones (Russell and Norvig, 2016). Regardless of the ML form chosen, ML applications use their algorithms to derive solutions to problems based on the data provided. Conversely, this means that the developers of ML systems no longer derive solutions to real-world problems themselves but describe problems based only on data, which is a significant difference from traditional (non-ML) information systems. (Mitchell, 1997; Russell and Norvig, 2016) Due to those unique characteristics, the development of ML systems requires a different approach than the development of non-ML systems.

Process models such as CRISP-DM (Wirth and Hipp, 2000) provide guidance and structure to projects developing data mining or machine learning applications. CRISP-DM structures respective projects into six consecutive phases (see Figure 1). In the *Business Understanding* phase, the project's business problem is identified and described by relevant performance metrics and requirements. On this basis, related data mining goals are derived. Relevant available data and meta-data sources are analyzed and characterized during the *Data Understanding* phase. The *Data Preparation* phase involves data cleaning, preprocessing, feature extraction, and selection to build useful datasets for the following stages. In the subsequent *Modeling* phase, machine learning algorithms are applied, primarily involving model selection and parameters training. The *Evaluation* phase typically relies on offline evaluation using held-out test data and suitable performance metrics (Jourdan et al., 2021). If the model fulfills the requirements defined in *Business Understanding*, it is subsequently deployed to production in the last phase (*Deployment*) (Wirth and Hipp, 2000).

Figure 1. Qualitative comparison of the CRISP-DM (Wirth and Hipp, 2000) model phases to the more recent CRISP-ML (Studer et al., 2021), which provides the structure for the categorization of challenges and derived design requirements.

The CRISP-DM model assumes that most of the described process, including the final evaluation, is performed offline using static datasets. Furthermore, it does not provide specific guidance for the time after the model is deployed to production. Thus, it does not cover the whole life cycle of an ML application. If a problem occurs after model deployment, a data scientist is expected to fix it. Here, a potential flaw becomes obvious: In dynamic environments which can be seen in industry 4.0, changes in data distributions are to be expected and should thus be addressed preemptively. Not addressing this issue risks performance degradation over time, which leads to false predictions and could cause errors

in subsequent systems as well as diminishing trust of the application's users (Yin, Wortman Vaughan and Wallach, 2019; Asatiani et al., 2021).

More recently, CRISP-ML has been proposed as a successor to CRISP-DM, intended to fix the aforementioned and other shortcomings (Studer et al., 2021). As one of the core contributions, CRISP-ML adds *Monitoring & Maintenance* as the last phase of the process model, where risks of model degradation in a changing environment are continually assessed, theoretically enabling the deployment of a model in a dynamic environment. The *Monitoring & Maintenance* task has strong connections to the concepts of DevOps and the more recent MLOps, as it touches both, data science as well as IT infrastructure related topics. The problems addressed by MLOps have first been mentioned by Sculley, Holt and Golovin (2015), where special kinds of technical debt are described that are unique to ML projects in contrast to classical software engineering projects. MLOps instruments aim at the standardization and streamlining of machine learning life cycle management (Treveil et al., 2020). Common elements of MLOps cover aspects related to automating, monitoring, testing, managing, and maintaining machine learning models and adjacent code in production through specialized tooling and design patterns (Lakshmanan, Robinson and Munn, 2020). In addition to adding *Monitoring & Maintenance*, CRISP-ML merges *Business Understanding* and *Data Understanding* into a single phase, arguing that they are strongly intertwined in practice as business objectives can be derived or changed based on the available data. While CRISP-ML provides a feasible structure for ML projects to integrate post-deployment ML system adaptation activities, it does not provide detailed guidance for sub-processes or system requirements. We draw upon CRISP-ML to structure the results of the expert interviews and the derived design requirements in the phases of the model, with the goal of addressing this distinct lack of guidance.

2.2 Sustainable long-term deployment of ML systems

In general, ML can be deployed to solve real-world problems and a set of data is required that represents this problem for training and testing of the ML model (e.g., Russell and Norvig, 2016). Model performance strongly depends on the data quantity and quality (Grover et al., 2018; Smith, 2020). Thus, the data used for ML models must be a good representation of the actual problem at hand (Mitchell, 1997). However, once an ML model is deployed, human perception of a problem may change (Russell and Norvig, 2016) or other factors lead to deviating conditions, risking model performance degradation in the long run (Sculley, Holt and Golovin, 2015; Sturm et al., 2021). Typically, this is caused by a shift or non-stationarity of the data and/or label distribution between the data used to train the model and the data available during inference in practical operation (Žliobaitė, 2010). In industry 4.0 applications, non-stationarity may be caused by various dynamic conditions such as tool and machine wear, changes in product configurations and material properties, changes in upstream processes, changes in factory layout and machine placement, differences in operator preferences and training, seasons, and time of day, environmental conditions such as temperature or humidity, sensor degradation, and data transmission problems (Jourdan et al., 2021). Current IS research on ML applications in organizations also highlights the need for continuous auditing and altering activities to maintain the performance and value of ML applications (e.g., Grønsund and Aanestad, 2020; Asatiani et al., 2021; Sturm et al., 2021). Multiple studies argue, for example, on the importance of continuously integrating human feedback when ML systems are deployed so that these models remain aligned with humans' dynamically changing understanding of the problem at hand (e.g., Stumpf et al., 2009; Russell and Norvig, 2016; Grønsund and Aanestad, 2020). Such human-in-the-loop patterns allow ML systems to adapt to end users after being deployed in an organization. Closely linking ML systems and end users through collaborative interaction is seen as beneficial for accomplishing a specific task in the moment, as well as increasing the system's accuracy over the long-term (e.g., Stumpf et al., 2009). Sturm et al. (2021) refer to activities related to adapting ML systems to the dynamically changing perception of a problem as *reconfiguration* of ML systems. *Reconfiguration* of ML systems may require multiple activities such as adapting criteria for data selection, the learning algorithm itself or settings of hyperparameters (e.g., Sculley, Holt and Golovin, 2015; Amershi et al., 2019; Sturm et al., 2021) and is often described as crucial for

continuously ensuring good ML performance (Sculley, Holt and Golovin, 2015; Amershi et al., 2019). In addition, an economic life cycle assessment of products, such as ML systems, also requires a positive trade-off of all incurred costs and economic benefits throughout the entire life cycle (Klöpffer, 2003). We argue that ML systems which by their nature consume large amounts of energy and human resources during development, should allow for a long-term deployment to continuously maintain and provide value. However, in the past ML systems in industry 4.0 have often not progressed beyond the concept development and prototyping stage (Metternich et al., 2021).

IS research recognizes this challenge and calls for methods to continuously adapt ML systems after their deployment (e.g., Audzeyeva and Hudson, 2016; Grønsund and Aanestad, 2020). However, solution approaches only intervene after a developed system has been deployed and are not sufficient to ensure ML systems provide the required adaptability for long-term deployment in dynamic environments such as industry 4.0. Van Wynsberghe (2021) further defines that sustainable AI requires a change in the entire lifecycle of AI products. We address this research call and see the need for a holistic approach that provides clear guidance on how to support long-term development throughout all stages of ML development and deployment. To do so, we aim to identify relevant challenges for the long-term operation of ML systems in the context of industry 4.0 and provide design requirements and principles to enable a sustainable deployment of ML applications.

3 Research Methodology

3.1 Design science research approach

We apply a DSR approach to address challenges for the sustainable long-term deployment of ML applications in industry 4.0. As DSR projects are feasible to find solutions for real-world problems, it allows us to ensure practical relevance as well as scientific rigor (Kuechler and Vaishnavi, 2008). The general design cycle according to Kuechler and Vaishnavi (2008) is structured into five distinct phases: *awareness of the problem*, *suggestion*, *development*, *evaluation* and *conclusion*. Our study focuses on the first two phases to identify key challenges, derive design requirements and instantiate a solution by formulating design principles. Within the *awareness of the problem* phase, we combine theoretical input from ML process models with non-theoretical input from experts, thus linking abstract theoretical knowledge with context-specific practical knowledge of industry 4.0 in an interplay (Kuechler and Vaishnavi, 2008; Meth, Mueller and Maedche, 2015). Based on semi-structured expert interviews, challenges for the development and the sustainable long-term deployment of ML applications in industry 4.0 are identified and general design requirements to address these challenges are derived. In the second phase (*suggestion*), we synthesize the results from the first phase of our DSR approach to develop design principles for solution instantiation. Gregor and Hevner (2013) define three levels of DSR contribution types ranging between specific, limited and less mature knowledge to abstract, complete and mature knowledge. While situated implementations of artifacts are classified as Level 1 contributions, operational design principles and constructs are considered Level 2 contributions, which can be further developed into design theories as Level 3 contributions. We thus provide a Level 2 contribution by transforming abstract and practical knowledge on long-term deployment of ML applications into operational design principles.

3.2 Semi-structured expert interviews

In this study, we conduct multiple expert interviews to gain practical insights into challenges that arise with the development and long-term deployment of ML models. We further discuss potential solution approaches that are feasible for implementation in continuously evolving industry 4.0 environments. We formulated a semi-structured interview guideline according to Sarker, Xiao and Beaulieu (2013). The semi-structured interview guideline comprises all relevant questions to identify challenges during all phases of the CRISP-ML process model while allowing interviewees to freely share further insights and experiences. Overall, 15 data science and machine learning experts of industry 4.0 start-ups, SMEs, and large companies were interviewed, as shown in Table 1. In addition to the goal of bringing in

extensive experience from various companies, experts fill both internal corporate roles as managers and data scientists as well as external consulting roles for ML in industry 4.0, or work as managers of software providers that offer software for ML applications in industry 4.0. All interviewees are involved in ML projects in both the development and deployment phases and therefore allow us to take our holistic approach and highlight the interrelationships of ML system design and long-term deployment in industry. While ML is being deployed in various industries today, we ensured that all interviewees are familiar with the development and deployment of ML models for industry 4.0 applications. Even though most ML applications in this sector have only emerged in the past decade, we were able to interview seven ML experts with more than 15 years of experience. Moreover, 13 interviewees had at least five years of experience in ML development for industry 4.0. All of the participants have already provided expert knowledge to various ML development teams prior to our study. In addition to general experience in ML development in industry 4.0, a majority of the participants (IP1,2,4,5,10,11,13,14) possess expertise in manufacturing quality control in the automotive and aerospace sectors. IP 8 and 9 also bring extensive experience in chemical product manufacturing to the study. IP 3 and 12 primarily gained experience in condition monitoring of machinery plants. After addressing interviewee-related questions to gain insights into their prior experience, current position, and the industries they have been working in, we provided the participants with an overview of the CRISP-DM and CRISP-ML process model. We then inquired whether the presented process models fit the interviewee's current approach of structuring ML projects within their respective companies. Subsequently, in the main part of the expert interviews, we walked through the CRISP-ML phases and specifically asked the interviewees, how these phases are usually implemented in their projects. In each phase, we investigated whether there is already consideration regarding reliability and long-term deployment and which specific challenges arose in past projects in this regard. Interviews were conducted from February to April 2022 via video call. After mutual agreement, all interviews were recorded and transcribed using the software Amberscript². On average, an interview lasted 52 minutes, and we were able to reach theoretical saturation during the last three interviews so that no further challenge was mentioned by the remaining interviewees (Flick, 2004).

Company Internal	External	
Data Scientist: ML Service Provider	Consultant: Operations and Industrial ML	Manager: Industrial ML Software Provider
IP1, IP2	IP7, IP8, IP9, IP10, IP11, IP12, IP13, IP14, IP15	IP3, IP4, IP5, IP6, IP7, IP8, IP9, IP10

Table 1. Overview of interviewee symbols and corresponding industry roles.

To evaluate and categorize the qualitative data gained through the interviews, we performed a content analysis (Weber, 1990; Myers and Newman, 2007). We applied an iterative multi-cycle coding process that comprised two coding cycles following the principles of Saldana (2021). During the first cycle, two types of coding were used. First, attribute coding allowed us to obtain relevant, descriptive information regarding the participants and their respective organizations. Descriptive coding was used next to identify challenges and solution approaches in the participants' statements. The second cycle covered pattern coding, which allowed us to build clusters of similar challenges but especially solution approaches for which we defined a large number of factors throughout the first cycle. In addition, a multi-researcher triangulation was applied. Two authors and one research assistant performed both coding cycles independently and derived an initial framework of identified challenges and the CRISP-ML process model. (Saldana, 2021) Before we merged the coding results of the researchers after each interview, the number of matching codes was derived which resulted in an average value of 74.2 %. Afterwards, all results were compared and discussed, and the final framework was derived based on this data analysis which further ensured rigor and trustworthiness.

4 Results

Within the following section, the challenges that were identified during the expert interviews are presented, combined with insights on possible solution approaches that practitioners use to address them.

We use the aforementioned categories based on the CRISP-ML process model for categorization. The results are summarized in Table 2. A number of challenges may occur in several phases of the process model. In the following, we assign these challenges to the phases where they were most often mentioned by the interviewed experts.

4.1 Challenges for long-term operation of ML systems in industry 4.0

The majority of interviewees saw the CRISP-ML process model as relatively close to the way they internally structure machine learning projects, even though, at the same time, most of the interviewees have only heard about the predecessor (CRISP-DM) prior to the interview. In addition, a number of interviewees (IP1,4,8,12,13,14,15) mentioned that CRISP-ML, compared to CRISP-DM, fits real projects better, as the additional *Monitoring and Maintenance* phase is crucial for practical deployment. However, interviewees also argued that the practical implementation of this phase is still rare, due to lacking standard solutions and the general novelty character of ML applications in the industry 4.0 sector. For example, an interviewee explained, *“Our ML development pretty much follows the CRISP-DM process model. But if I’m honest, we’re primarily concerned with delivering models, and processes become – let’s say - less standardized after deployment. So we really need something like a monitoring and maintenance phase, but right now I would say we rather intervene in emergencies only”* (IP9).

Business and Data Understanding. A frequently mentioned challenge (IP1,4,5,9,10,11), is the expectation management of the shareholders, especially of customers who are not familiar with ML and data science. This challenge may manifest in two very distinct ways, with customers either having unrealistic expectations about the possible performance achievements of ML models (IP5,12,13,15), especially given the available data basis in their use case, or customers being extremely skeptical regarding the use of ML models, not trusting their performance. In the latter case, the usage of either simple or otherwise explainable ML algorithms is seen as a possible solution approach. The alignment of sales and engineering departments is named as another problem in this context as it is hard but critical to align business goals with the uncertainty of ML development, especially regarding specific levels of application performance (IP12). Specifying requirements with respect to robustness is also named as a challenge by the interviewees. A set of operating conditions the application needs to handle must be identified as well as different operating modes of the machine or production line (IP2,6,11). In this context, the integration of domain knowledge is seen as crucial. An interviewee stated, *“We still face this problem that our customers ask us to develop ML systems that should solve all their problems at once, but at the same time it is quite hard for them to define under which conditions this system will be operated in one, two or five years”* (IP11). A fundamental and often encountered problem during *Business and Data Understanding* is missing meta-data in the form of time-series annotations related to, e.g., maintenance activities or machine breakdowns (IP1,3,4,5,6,8,12,13). This data is crucial for data analysis and for the training of supervised ML models. Thus, an alternative approach is the usage of unsupervised ML algorithms, which is not suitable in all use case scenarios though. Further problems with meta-data include privacy issues if the data can be connected to the performance of specific employees (IP12). Poor data quality is another issue (IP11,12,13). At the same time, interviewees describe the achievable solution quality as mostly dependent on data quality, quantity, and variety (IP4,5,12). Interviewees note that it is hard to estimate the quantity and variety of data at the beginning of the project (IP1,4,6,11,13) and that a first analysis is usually done with smaller datasets. Analysis frequently reveals that more data is needed for a given problem than available (IP1,4,5,6,11,12,13,15), often leading to the cancellation of a project. Interesting events such as machine breakdowns or product defects are usually rare in a dataset (IP5,6,10,15). Furthermore, time dependencies such as seasonality are described as problematic as these usually require an increasing amount of data to be modeled but are a key aspect for long-term operation (IP5,6,11,12,13). One interviewee explained, *“Whatever challenge we face, in the end it’s always about data. Before development, we often don’t know what we need or we do not have the data needed and in the end data drifts and other changes kind of force us to reconsider if our trained models are still useful”* (IP5).

Data Preparation. While the *Data Preparation* phase itself is a frequently mentioned general challenge as it takes a significant portion of the total project time, it was not specifically mentioned as impeding the sustainability or long-term operation of the ML models by the interviewees.

Modeling. Interviewees see the tradeoff between simple and complex ML models as a particular challenge during the modeling phase. While complex models such as deep neural networks may provide high capacities to model complicated functions, they are often more prone to overfitting, which is detrimental to their robustness (IP4,11,15). It was further mentioned that those simpler models should be preferred if it has no impact on performance or lower performance is acceptable for the given use case as they commonly provide better explainability (IP5,6,8,10) and “*customer acceptance is much better for simple and interpretable models*” (IP6). Such a model selection strategy is referred to as Occam’s razor which was explicitly mentioned by two experts (IP11,15). Interviewees further mentioned that model-agnostic techniques for explainable AI may be used to provide explainability of complex models. However, they increase overall system complexity and the results are often hard to interpret in practice (IP8,10). Besides that, one interviewee mentioned that they almost “*exclusively use unsupervised approaches in manufacturing projects, because labeled data is rarely available in sufficient quality and quantity*”, and target variables such as fault types may change over time (IP4). A frequently mentioned general challenge related to modeling (IP2,4,5,11,13), is the scalability of models to different instances of machines or production lines. It is indicated, that even if a customer utilizes multiple instances of the exact same machine or production line, a model that was trained on data of either one of the instances or a held-out instance on a test bench, does not perform well if deployed to other instances, as the data distribution already differs too strongly. Possible reasons are sensor placement, differences in manufacturing processes as well as human operator preferences. This problem is described as especially severe in predictive maintenance applications which are strongly dependent on the machine specifics (IP5,9,13,15). Possible strategies for mitigation of this problem include transfer-learning or fine-tuning of a trained model using smaller datasets of the target machine or production line (IP9,13).

Evaluation. While most interviewees mention that evaluation of the ML models is commonly performed using an offline held-out test set it is often noted that this kind of evaluation is not sufficient for real-world applications. Interviewees suggested that the model’s robustness needs to be explicitly tested, by focusing on edge cases in the input data, which can be found using statistical analysis of the datasets (IP2,5,6,11). Test cases might then be generated using Monte-Carlo simulation or design of experiments (IP2,6). In addition to this offline evaluation, an interviewee mentioned “*For us, it is crucial to evaluate the model before and after deployment and we were surprised how many problems can only be revealed after deployment. You simply cannot detect all these issues with a static test dataset beforehand*” (IP4). Corresponding issues include data quality problems and non-stationarity of the data that was not noticed during development (IP1,13). If possible, a pre-existing application for the use case or frequent manual checks should be run in parallel in the test phase for output validation (IP9,10,14,15).

Deployment. During deployment, primarily organizational and IT infrastructure-related challenges were mentioned by the interviewees. In the scope of this study, they are of special interest, as these are typically issues that do not arise in academic work but are crucial for practitioners. Especially challenging is the interfacing of the application to various subsystems or data acquisition devices (IP5,6,11,13). An interviewee explained “*You know, we follow all these theoretical guidelines, but once you get close to deploy such ML systems, it is always a mess. Hundreds of different systems must interface with our application. It’s exhausting and I don’t see our customers taking on this task and better yet doing it repeatedly on their own with their current setup*” (IP11). A possible solution approach can be the usage of standardized interfaces such as Open Platform Communications - Unified Architecture (OPC-UA). Furthermore, it is critical to automate and document the deployment process in such a way that it is repeatable in the monitoring and maintenance phase (IP2,5), building on the principles of DevOps and MLOps. This issue was emphasized in the case of deployment on edge devices.

Monitoring and Maintenance. As *Monitoring and Maintenance* is a key phase of the CRISP-ML model with regard to sustainable deployment, the majority of mentioned challenges are of this category. Most interviewees agreed that this phase is paramount for long-term deployment, as “*ML models only provide*

value in situations that are shown in the dataset” (IP2). In this context, an interviewee referred to deployed ML models as “only ever meta-stable” (IP12). When something changes or the data distribution is non-stationary, the performance of the ML model will most likely strongly degrade and the model requires updating (IP1,4,5,6,9,10,11,12,13,14,15). Four, often experienced sources of change were mentioned in the interviews: Sensor drift (IP1,4,5,6), seasonalities or time dependencies not identified during development (IP5,11,15), changes in the configuration of the machine or the product (IP1,3,12,13) and network or hardware problems that render their respective data sources invalid or non-available (IP6,12). This yields two additional challenges: The detection of a change, as well as the adjustment of the processing pipeline, i.e., updating of the model, because drifts and changes impact sensor data which is used as an input for the ML model in operation.

A number of interviewees mentioned that it is primarily important to monitor the properties of the input data (IP2,6,8). Statistical measures can be used to capture properties of the training data that are then compared to the live data during operation. Suitable measures include distribution distance metrics or simple thresholds. The complexity of the monitoring task rises with the number of data sources. Automatic checks within the processing pipeline are often used to detect the described changes. In addition to the input data, it was mentioned that the model error rate should be monitored too, as monitoring of the input data is only a proxy to this quantity (IP1,2,11,14). An interviewee mentioned “Even though it is still a challenging task, we are already able to partially automate some monitoring activities. But if we want to update a model, this is a manual and often tedious task and we really need to improve this” (IP2). In addition to issues related to data science or machine learning, interviewees describe several challenges that relate to IT infrastructure in this phase. Model updates can be a challenging task since it requires access to datasets, training infrastructure, and the deployed model which often runs on an edge device. While cloud computing solutions such as Microsoft Azure or Amazon Web Services (AWS) offer standardized pipelines for data collection, management, model training, and cloud deployment, edge deployment is still an issue. In this context, data security and privacy are seen as additional challenges (IP5,6,11,12,13) that prevent customers from relying on cloud solutions. If automatic deployment is not an option, data scientists require physical access to the computing devices. Again, the interviewees indicated that a large variety of data sources to a model and thus connected subsystems increase complexity. Extensive logging during operation is therefore important to quickly analyze application errors and find their root causes (IP1,6). Although challenging, *Monitoring and Maintenance* of ML models is seen as a viable addition to the business model of ML solution providers as mentioned both by manufacturing company internal and external interviewees (IP1,6,8,10,11,12,13,14,15) as it “provides a constant revenue stream whereas, you know, for this prior development process, we usually agree on project-based fixed-term work and payment” (IP15). At the same time, this may provide another challenge, as *Monitoring and Maintenance* activities are often not covered by the initial development contracts. Multiple interviewees stated that robustness and sustainable, long-term use of ML applications have only recently become a focus of their work, as the productive usage of ML applications has only slowly become a reality in the last years and the number of deployed models is still relatively small (IP1,12,14,15). An associated challenge that was mentioned by the interviewees is the lack of a standard / best-practice solution for *Monitoring and Maintenance* of ML applications in industrial environments (IP1,2,6,12,14). A manager of a large ML software provider stated “Never change a running system – that’s something I hear quite often from our customers in this context and it’s really slowing us down. I’m convinced that we will provide services to maintain ML systems in the future, but to do that we need to reduce the complexity of these systems. [...] So I advocate for future projects to keep ML system maintenance in mind from the beginning and consider that in, yeah, pretty much every future system design” (IP13).

4.2 Deriving design requirements and principles for a solution instantiation

Following the identification of challenges through expert interviews, we derive solution approaches as design requirements and structure them along the CRISP-ML process model. Overall, we pose nine requirements that address challenges mentioned by interviewees as outlined in Table 2. First, uncertainty that is often associated with ML development projects, raises concerns of customers and customer

expectation management remains a challenge today. To align expectations, address data privacy concerns and integrate domain knowledge in the very beginning of ML development, we propose **DR1: Collaboratively align system requirements with stakeholders**. Second, data preparation remains a tedious process and especially labeling of data requires significant resources which would also be required for future retraining of algorithms as a *reconfiguration* activity for long-term use of ML systems. Algorithms from the field of unsupervised learning that do not require labeled data for training were mentioned as feasible to ease this process. We therefore propose **DR2: Use unsupervised ML algorithms, if possible**.

CRISP-ML Phase	Challenges	Design Requirements
<i>Business and Data Understanding</i>	Customer expectation management	DR1 Collaboratively align system requirements with stakeholders
	Customer acceptance	
	Domain knowledge integration	DR2 Use unsupervised ML algorithms, if possible
	Data privacy and security	
	Limited quantity and quality of data	DR3 Design for a comprehensive range of operating conditions and their boundaries
	Limited availability of meta-data or labels	
	Requirements definition regarding robustness and data variety	
Time dependencies and seasonalities in data	DR4 Use simple models and explainable AI-techniques	
<i>Modeling</i>		Trade-off between simple and complex models: Capacity, explainability, computational requirements
	Scalability of models to different instances of machines or production lines	DR5 Use transfer learning techniques such as domain adaptation
<i>Evaluation</i>	Offline evaluation not sufficient for real-world applications	DR6 Continuously and frequently evaluate model performance
	Unnoticed non-stationarities in the data	
<i>Deployment</i>	Interfacing and integration to various IT-systems such as MES and ERP	DR7 Maximize use of standardized interfaces
	Retrofit of sensors complicated due to required line (re-)certification / qualification	
	Time consuming deployment processes	DR8 Maximize automation of testing and deployment, e.g. MLOps and DevOps
	Automated deployment to edge devices	
<i>Monitoring and Maintenance</i>	Data drift due to seasonality, time dependencies, configuration changes, network and hardware problems	DR9 Monitor model confidence and input data using statistical measures
	Change detection	
	Model updates	
	Missing standardized solutions, lacking automation of tasks	

Table 2: Challenges and corresponding solution approaches identified as design requirements.

Third, variances in operating conditions and other influencing factors should be considered from the outset to cope with future data shifts or time dependencies. To ensure robustness of models in the long-term and ensure necessary data variety, we propose **DR3: Design for a comprehensive range of operating conditions and their boundaries**. Fourth, while performance of ML systems was not mentioned as a major challenge by any of the interviewees, explainability of models and limitations in capacity were often seen as a challenge for developers that hinders maintenance of models in the future and further risks customer acceptance. A trade-off is seen between simple, explainable models and

complex models with potentially higher performance. We thus recommend to follow Occam's razor during model selection and resort to simpler models if the use case allows for it, while resorting to explicit techniques for explainable AI if complex models are required. This yields **DR4: Use simple models and explainable AI-techniques**. Fifth, to allow for scalability of ML systems to e.g. other machines or plants in industry 4.0 environments or cope with varying operating conditions, ML models require adaption in the future. We therefore propose **DR5: Use transfer learning techniques such as domain adaptation**. Sixth, non-stationarities in data often cause offline model performance evaluations to deviate from evaluations conducted after deployment. To detect declining model performance in time during operation before models are no longer usable, we propose **DR6: Continuously and frequently evaluate model performance**. The deployment of ML systems often involves a difficult and time consuming process of integration and interfacing with IT systems to access the required data streams. To ensure continuous development of ML systems and maintain their value over time, models will be deployed regularly during the *Monitoring & Maintenance* phase of CRISP-ML and this process should be as simple and automated as possible. MLOps and DevOps were mentioned as promising solution approaches to closely link machine learning related continuous development activities and IT operations of organizations in industry 4.0. We thus propose **DR7: Maximize use of standardized interfaces**, and **DR8: Maximize automation of testing and deployment, e.g. through MLOps and DevOps techniques**. Lastly, transfer learning techniques can be used to adapt ML systems after deployment (see **DR5** for the *Modeling* phase) to cope with data drifts, time dependencies, configuration changes or any other aberrant conditions. However, organizations in industry 4.0 that want to leverage ML systems over longer periods of time need to continuously monitor input data and model performance to decide when system updates are needed. Therefore, we propose **DR9: Monitor model confidence and input data using statistical measures**.

Following the derivation of general design requirements, we formulated overarching action-oriented design principles as outlined in Figure 2. DPs are assigned to specific DRs which were derived from the identified challenges. However, as suggested by Hevner et al. (2004), design principles can serve on the one hand as an actionable blueprint for e.g. a prototypical implementation of ML artefacts, but on the other hand can also be used as testable hypotheses for future research work. In addition, DPs support an holistic approach to ML system development and deployment that closely links all phases of the CRISP-ML process model. To address the core problem of ML applications being deployed in dynamic environments such as industry 4.0, where problem perception and other operating conditions may continuously change, ML applications require flexibility to be deployed in and adapted to varying conditions. We therefore propose **DP1: Continuously provide ML applications with sufficient training and testing data that covers all relevant operating conditions and evaluative capabilities to verify both databases are aligned with real-world dynamics**. To detect deviating conditions which could lead to a declining performance of ML models over time, systems require self-monitoring capabilities and human-machine interfaces that allow system operators to understand emerging discrepancies. To address these challenges, we propose **DP2: Provide ML applications with continuous mechanism that detects data drifts or changes in the certainty of the model and capabilities to transparently present these dynamics to the responsible system user**. Besides the adaption to dynamic environmental conditions, ML systems that required large resources for development, should allow for scalability to maximize the provided value over time. Therefore, by building on techniques from the domain adaptation area, we propose **DP3: Provide ML applications with capabilities that allow for scaling their area of operation and adapt them to dynamic environmental changes**. In the past, much attention was paid to the development of complex algorithms to maximize ML model performance. However, our interview study showed that model performance was of less interest and the explainability of models has emerged as a major challenge today, on the one hand for customer acceptance but also in the long run for the maintenance of ML systems. Oftentimes, maintenance or reconfiguration activities (e.g. retraining of ML models) will be performed by people other than the original system developers. We therefore propose **DP4: Provide ML applications with capabilities to meet defined performance while resorting to simple models to ensure that decisions are presented in a way that is understandable to the responsible system user**. Although monitoring and maintenance of ML systems has only recently

become a focal point in many industry 4.0 projects, related activities such as retraining and deployment of updated models should be performed frequently in the future. To facilitate this process, automation and user support are of key interest. We therefore derive **DP5: Provide ML applications with mechanisms for automatic testing and deployment and provide features that, if necessary, alert the responsible system user.** Interviewees frequently mentioned the tedious process of integrating ML systems into the existing IT landscape of industry 4.0 environments. Scalability as well as the continuous integration of newly acquired data streams should become a key capability of ML systems to allow for a more sustainable long-term deployment which further supports customer acceptance. Thus, ML projects should strive for standardized interfaces to ease this process and we propose **DP6: Build ML applications upon standardized interfaces for maximum compatibility and use simple ML models to facilitate the definition and integration of evolving data requirements.**

→	Design Principles	
DR3 DR5 DR6	DP1	Continuously provide ML applications with sufficient training and testing data that covers all relevant operating conditions and evaluative capabilities to verify both databases are aligned with real-world dynamics.
DR6 DR9	DP2	Provide ML applications with a continuous mechanism that detects data drifts or changes in the certainty of the model and capabilities to transparently present these dynamics to the responsible system user.
DR3 DR5	DP3	Provide ML applications with capabilities that allow for scaling their area of operation and adapt them to dynamic environmental changes.
DR1 DR2 DR4	DP4	Provide ML applications with capabilities to meet defined performance while resorting to simple models to ensure that decisions are presented in a way that is understandable to the responsible system user.
DR2 DR8	DP5	Provide ML applications with mechanisms for automatic testing and deployment and provide features that, if necessary, alert the responsible system user.
DR1 DR4 DR7	DP6	Build ML applications upon standardized interfaces for maximum compatibility and use simple ML models to facilitate the definition and integration of evolving data requirements.

Figure 2: Design principles for ML applications suitable for long-term deployment in dynamic environments.

5 Discussion and Conclusion

Due to the increasing availability of data in the industry 4.0 sector, ML applications slowly transcend from academia to practical applications. However, the level of adoption and actual reliance on these applications is still low and questions about reliability, sustainable long-term use and robustness remain largely unanswered. Research on ML applications in organizations highlight the need for continuous auditing and altering activities to enable ML systems to provide long-term value (e.g., Grønsund and Aanestad, 2020; Asatiani et al., 2021; Sturm et al., 2021). We follow a DSR approach to identify which challenges impede practitioners in the sustainable long-term deployment of ML in the context of real-world industry 4.0 applications with a focus on monitoring and maintenance of ML systems and thus address **RQ1**. The identified challenges cover most phases in the lifecycle of an ML model, starting with the initial project specifications and ending with the continuous monitoring and maintenance. Semi-structured expert interviews were performed and besides challenges, corresponding solution approaches were inductively derived and transformed into tangible design requirements for ML system to support long-term operation. In addition, action-oriented design principles were formulated that link all phases of development and deployment to support a holistic approach, thus addressing **RQ2**. IS researchers and ML system developers can use DRs and DPs derived in this study for guidance in how to design ML

systems that allow for a more sustainable long-term use and maintain their value over time. As suggested by Kuechler and Vaishnavi (2008), we will continue our DSR approach by instantiating an ML system as a suggested solution within an industry 4.0 environment based on our DPs. Consequently, we will evaluate the extent to which the consideration of our DPs supports the adaptation of our ML system to dynamic environmental changes by simulating long-term deployment through various data drifts. Feedback will be incorporated into several design cycles.

The presented research yields several **contributions** for academia as well as practitioners. First, we provide a structured overview of the challenges currently hindering long-term deployment of ML systems in dynamic environments such as industry 4.0. On the one hand, it is crucial to understand and contextualize these challenges in order to align research work more closely with the needs of practitioners. On the other hand, this deeper understanding enables us to redesign the way we develop ML applications today to ensure sustainable long-term use. Second, we extend research on sustainable ML which primarily focuses on sustainable use cases for ML to sustainable ML product development that focuses on maintaining the value of ML applications over time. Broad applicability of the provided challenge-design-requirement framework in the industry 4.0 sector creates a common starting point for targeted design of sustainable IS artifacts in the future. Finally, our study addresses the call for future work in IS research on adapting ML systems to dynamic changes in problem perception (e.g., Grønsund and Aanestad, 2020). We extend that call for research by showing the multitude of potential challenges in dynamic environments such as industry 4.0 and provide a holistic approach that considers all phases of ML system development and deployment. Furthermore, the derived DRs and DPs provide a basis for future research in the field of sustainable long-term deployment of ML as well as clear guidance for researchers and practitioners to integrate sustainability into the core of every ML system and to create acceptance for resource-intensive technology development that enables the efficiency of industrial processes to keep pace with the rapid developments in the interconnected world and to secure competitive advantages in the long term.

At the same time, this study faces **limitations** that need to be considered when using the results. First, the number of interviewees is limited, which may bias the results towards certain subsectors of industry 4.0. However, due to the vast experience, diversity and internationality of the interviewees, we are confident in the validity of the results of the study. Second, due to the qualitative nature of this study, the severity of the challenges cannot be easily quantified and thus the challenges cannot be prioritized. Lastly, the derived DRs and DPs have not yet been evaluated. This study yields ample opportunities for future work, both regarding the limitations of the study itself as well as in addressing the identified challenges and derived DRs and DPs. While we plan to implement and test the DRs and DPs in a prototype ML application as part of a follow-up study, we also invite **future research** to evaluate our design guidelines in a wide variety of dynamic environments. Moreover, it is to be expected that challenges will differ to a certain degree, depending on the specific industry that is analyzed, which should be examined in separate studies to refine DRs and DPs. While derived DRs and DPs can support and facilitate the process of maintaining an ML application over time, organizations still need to provide an infrastructure for adapting ML models to, for example, data drifts, and train their workforce in MLOps and DevOps techniques, as well as in new areas of research such as domain adaptation.

Interestingly, lacking performance of existing ML algorithms was never mentioned as a challenge during the interviews, thereby highlighting the importance of holistic research that focuses on integration and long-term deployment of ML in contrast to focusing on optimizing benchmark dataset scores or developing more complex algorithms.

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